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Second release of experiment centric and composite-AI tools

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF TABLES	4
LIST OF FIGURES	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1 - INTRODUCTION	5
Objectives	5
Architecture overview	5
2 - STATUS OF AI4EOSC 2 IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	6
3 - NEW FEATURES FOR AI4EOSC 2ND RELEASE	7
New code repositories	8
New PAPI functionalities	9
External integrations	9
Try-me endpoints	10
Inference endpoints	10
AI4compose implementation	11
Elyra Nodes	11
Node-RED	13
New tools	16
CVAT	16
Kafka	17
NVFLARE	17
Small LLMs	18
User centric dashboard	18
Model and data versioning	24
Drift monitoring tools	25
Model provenance	27
Model metadata tools	28
Train batch mode	29
AI4OS LLM	29
New authentication	30
4 - USER JOURNEYS TO THE PLATFORM	30
Try a model	30
Develop a model	31
Train a model	32
Deploy a model	33
5 - CONCLUSION	34
REFERENCES	34

LIST OF TABLES

- Table 1: Status of the roadmap for AI4EOSC 2.
- Table 2: Elyra custom nodes provided by AI4Compose.
- Table 3: Node-RED custom nodes provided by AI4Compose.

LIST OF FIGURES

- Figure 1: Location of WP5 components within the overall platform architecture.
- Figure 2: Cross-disciplinary pipeline created in Node-RED.
- Figure 3: Modules catalog view in the AI4EOSC Dashboard.
- Figure 4: AI4EOSC module detail view.
- Figure 5: Applied filters detail.
- Figure 6: Configuration form of the Federated Learning Server with the Flower software.
- Figure 7: CVAT Image Annotation tool detail view.
- Figure 8: Inference button inside AI4EOSC module detail view.
- Figure 9: Profile section.
- Figure 10: Data configuration section
- Figure 11: Configuration form of an LLM deployment.
- Figure 12: MLflow Experiment-run example where input dataset is tracked
- Figure 13: Data drift visualisation of the OBSEA-FISH Detector Model from AI4EOSC Catalog
- Figure 14: Graph visualization of the provenance RDF file of an AI module.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the new features for services developed in WP5 that have been implemented during the second part of the AI4EOSC project. We start by giving a high level overview of the status of the features outlined in the Roadmap for the second release. Then, we describe each of the features implemented, including those that were not initially planned in the project roadmap. Finally, we show how the different features are successfully used in standard user workflows.

1 - INTRODUCTION

OBJECTIVES

The main purpose of this deliverable is to describe the features implemented during the second part of the project within the scope of WP5. These features were developed in response to the AI4OS 2 roadmap initially designed in Deliverable 5.2 [D5.2], then updated in Deliverable 5.3 [D5.3].

This deliverable is complementary to Deliverable D5.5 [D5.5], which is dedicated to the final implementation of components. This deliverable (D5.4) will provide a high-level overview of the features implemented, while D5.5 will focus on the technical implementation behind those features. A key difference is also that this deliverable focuses only on the second part of the project, while D5.5 will also cover features developed within the first part of the project (as they are relevant for the final implementation).

In [Section 2](#), we give a brief overview of the completion status of the different features sketched in the roadmap, while in [Section 3](#) we comment on those features in more detail. Finally in [Section 4](#) we describe how those features are used in several typical user-oriented workflows in the platform.

ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

In this section we provide in [Figure 1](#) a quick reminder of the location of WP5 components within the overall platform architecture. Bear in mind that some components might be at the intersection between different Work Packages.

For a quick table overview of each of the components, please refer to deliverable D3.4 [D3.4]. The tables also provide endpoints of where the components can be accessed, as well as the code repos where the implementations described in this deliverable are located.

Figure 1: Location of WP5 components within the overall platform architecture.

2 - STATUS OF AI4EOSC 2 IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

In Deliverable 5.2 [D5.2], we provided an implementation plan for the AI4EOSC 2nd release. Subsequently, in Deliverable 5.3 [D5.3], we updated that original implementation plan, according to the project's evolution.

In this section, we will give an overview on the completion status of that updated implementation plan. For a detailed account of the new implemented features, please refer to Section 3.

Table 1: Status of the roadmap for AI4EOSC 2. Color code: (●) for completed work, (●) for partially completed work, (●) for work that didn't need to be completed after reevaluation.

Component/Actions	Status + Description
New code repositories	● New metadata version was deployed. The redesign of the CI/CD pipeline was completed.
New PAPI functionalities	● Statistics retrieval was implemented. Deployments are done in a federated cluster. Email notifications are active. Tighter integration with Vault was completed. Shelving of deployments was implemented.

Component/Actions	Status + Description
External integrations	● Integration of external datasets (via DataHugger) and marketplaces (e.g. AI4Life) has been carried out.
Try endpoints	● Deployed try-me endpoints with Gradio UI was implemented.
Inference endpoints	● Multiple inference options were implemented, both serverless and server based.
AI4Compose implementation	● Additional nodes were created for models, result composition and use cases.
New tools (eg. CVAT, Kafka)	● New tools were added (CVAT, NVFlare, LLMs)
User centric Dashboard	● Statistics section was added. Module filtering was improved. Closer integration with storage was completed.
Model and data versionings	● MLflow model versioning was included in the documentation. Closer integration with Vault was completed.
Drift monitoring tools	● Driftwatch service to monitor data drift in inference deployments was deployed.
Model provenance	● The provenance tracking service was created..
Model metadata tools	● Tools to manage metadata were created. Integration with the MLDCAT-AP standard was implemented.

3 - NEW FEATURES FOR AI4EOSC 2ND RELEASE

In this section we will describe the new features available in the AI4EOSC 2nd release. We will explain both the features originally described in the AI4EOSC 2 Updated implementation plan [\[D5.3\]](#), as well as the new features that we added on top of it.

When applicable, we will include links to the specific official documentation [\[ai4-docs\]](#) where a specific feature is described.

NEW CODE REPOSITORIES

As stated in D5.3, the migration of modules was successfully carried out. All modules are now hosted in the common **ai4os-hub** Github organization [\[ai4-catalogs\]](#) and, for each module, now the code and the Docker files are hosted under a single unified repository.

Additionally, we developed a new metadata schema with new additional fields, including a richer description of the modules [\[ai4-docs\]](#). New fields include:

- **categories** (e.g. "AI4 trainable", "AI4 inference"),
- **tasks** (e.g. "Computer Vision", "Classification"),
- **libraries** (e.g. "TensorFlow", "PyTorch"),
- **data type** (e.g. "Image", "Text"),
- **inference** (to provide an optimal recommended amount of computing resources your module needs to perform training),
- **provenance** (to provide information on how your module was trained).

All these new fields allow for a richer description of modules, permeating different components like the new filtering functionalities in the **Dashboard** and in the RDF generation in the **Provenance** component.

The metadata validation is performed with the newly developed **AI4OS metadata tool**. This tool allows users to convert the metadata to support profiles (like MLDCAT-AP [\[mldcat-ap\]](#)) and formats (like JSON-LD [\[json-ld\]](#) and RD Turtle [\[turtle\]](#)), developed in collaboration with the SEMIC support center [\[semic\]](#).

Finally, we migrated the CI/CD Jenkins pipeline to JePL v2 [\[jep1\]](#). The Continuous Integration is now a combination of user-defined steps and steps performed on the platform side. The latter enables us to easily implement common steps that will run for all modules, without having to modify the Pipeline of each single module, enforcing all the necessary quality checks and further integrations at a platform-wide level².

User-defined steps usually ensure model quality, by performing tests using tox [\[tox\]](#):

- Code style analysis with flake8 [\[flake8\]](#);
- Unit testing of the module's functionality using pytest [\[pytest\]](#);
- Security scanners using bandit [\[bandit\]](#).

While **platform-wide steps** are common for all modules:

- Metadata validation using the **AI4OS metadata tool**;
- Rebuild of Docker images into our Harbor registry, also mirroring to Docker Hub [\[dockerhub\]](#);
- Updating related AI4OS components, like updating the module metadata in the Platform API or updating the Docker images in the OSCAR cluster;
- Archiving the code in Zenodo [\[zenodo\]](#) if a Github release was made in the code repository
- Triggering the **Provenance** service, that parses the information from the rest of the components.

² <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/reference/modules.html#ci-cd-pipeline>

NEW PAPI FUNCTIONALITIES

The Platform API (PAPI) has continued to evolve to support the project's development. During this second half of the project, we have accomplished many of the milestones stated in the D5.3 Roadmap, including:

- Support for **statistics**: PAPI now retrieves current usage and historical usage statistics for both individual users and for the whole VO. We also retrieve statistics about the current platform status;
- Support to **deploy user jobs in a federated cluster**;
- Automation of **email notifications** when a job takes long to deploy;
- Integration with the Vault **secrets management**;
- Support for **shelving deployments**, so that the users can pause their work when they don't need the resources and restart whenever they like.

Additionally, we developed features on top of what was stated in D5.3, including the ability to **deploy batch jobs**.

In addition, as a central point of integration of platform components, many of the new features described in this deliverable have required changes in PAPI, including **New tools**, **Train batch mode**, **Try endpoints**, **Inference endpoints**, **External dataset integrations**, **AI4OS LLM** and **New code repositories**.

EXTERNAL INTEGRATIONS

As stated in D5.3, we developed two kinds of external integrations.

First, we **integrated external datasets**. For this we used datahugger [[datahugger](#)] inside the Nomad jobs deployed in the Workload Management System. Every time a user makes a deployment from the dashboard, they can choose to provide a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and the dataset will be downloaded in their storage during deployment. This dataset will be automatically available in the deployment workspace, ready to use. On top of providing directly the DOI, we have implemented in the Dashboard a visual tool to directly select datasets from Zenodo. We also contributed to the tool with several additional data providers, like SeaNoe or Data Europa [[datahugger-contrib](#)].

Second, we **integrated external model marketplaces**. As a first use case for this integration, we integrated the Biolmage Zoo [[bioimage-zoo](#)] from the AI4life project [[ai4life](#)]. For this we developed a custom connector, in the form of a new AI4OS tool. Given a specific Bioimage model ID, this tool is able to retrieve the model metadata. Then, it is able to expose the model's functionality behind our DEEPaaS API by reading the model's inputs/outputs, thus making it compatible with the AI4EOSC catalog. On top of this, deployed Biolmage models can be used with a custom Gradio interface we developed explicitly for them.

Finally, for better user experience, compatible Biolmage models are shown in a dedicated tab in the Dashboard marketplace, with a custom module detail mapping Biolmage metadata to AI4OS metadata. Although available for all users, we decided to deploy a dedicated Dashboard for AI4life users [[ai4life-dashboard](#)], with dedicated resources, to better highlight this strong collaboration.

TRY-ME ENDPOINTS

In respect to inference, we have implemented try-me endpoints based on Nomad³. Any user can now enter the Dashboard, select any module and a deployment will be created without further customization. Users are able to interact with the model via a Gradio interface [gradio]. To be able to open this feature to any user (even non-project members), we have restricted the deployment duration to 10 minutes as well as limited the number of simultaneous deployments a single user can make.

In the initial Roadmap, we considered including an endpoint based on OSCAR, permanently deployed for the most popular modules, so that users could try the models instantly. For this purpose, the “*exposed services*” feature was developed as part of OSCAR [oscar]. But reconsidering the user interaction with the try-me endpoints, we decided to follow an alternative approach. We kept only the Nomad try option, but under-the-hood those deployments were made in a dedicated compute node, where the Docker images are prefetched. This allowed us to avoid consuming resources constantly (even when try-me endpoints were not used) while still allowing for a *near instantaneous* deployment of modules.

INFERENCE ENDPOINTS

We have developed multiple options to deploy models for inference [ai4-docs]. In contrast with try-me endpoints, inference endpoints are production oriented, allowing for a more extensive resource usage, and are thus restricted to project members.

As from the initial roadmap, we have implemented two main options to deploy modules within the platform, which are meant to address complementary user needs.

The first adopts the **OSCAR** Inference Platform so that users can deploy any module in serverless mode⁴. Some of the main advantages of this functionality are as follows::

- Modules only consume resources when they are in use, at the cost of some extra latency for the model to be deployed before making a prediction;
- Model can automatically scale the resources used to accommodate peaks in queries;
- Support for both sync and async calls;
- Support for predictions via default OSCAR UI;
- The technical configuration steps are handled by the platform when creating the endpoint via the Dashboard;
- Manual configuration of the endpoint is still possible for customized needs (eg. historical batch predictions) when creating the model via the OSCAR UI.

The latter adopts the **Nomad** cluster, users are able to deploy any module in dedicated mode, where the user gets a permanent deployment on dedicated resources⁵. This has several benefits including:

- Low latency in predictions, at the cost of consuming resources even when not actively making predictions;

³ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/try/dashboard-gradio.html#>

⁴ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/deploy/oscar.html>

⁵ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/deploy/nomad.html>

- Support for sync calls;
- Support for predictions via dedicated Gradio UI;
- The technical configuration steps are handled by the platform when creating the endpoint via the Dashboard.

In addition to the platform deployment options, we offer several options to deploy your model externally.

First, you can use the **Infrastructure Manager [im] [D4.5]** to deploy your model in any external cloud. This allows you to deploy your model in resources you control at the cost of having to deal with the technical configuration needed to expose the model functionality.

Second, you can deploy in the **EU Node [eu-node]**, which offers limited free computing resources to any EU researcher. For this purpose, we have developed new tools in the Tools Hub, allowing users to deploy modules both as VM and container resources.

AI4COMPOSE IMPLEMENTATION

During the last period of the project, as stated in D5.3, we have focused our effort on AI4Compose in developing and testing new pipelines offered as ready-to-use nodes both for Elyra and Node-RED environments.

Elyra Nodes

As part of the second release of experiment-centric and composite AI tools, the set of Elyra nodes **[elyra]** has been extended to support building visual AI pipelines directly within Jupyter Notebook environments. These nodes allow users to call OSCAR services by providing only the essential parameters, such as the endpoint, service name, and access token. This makes it straightforward to integrate inference models deployed on OSCAR clusters into notebook workflows with a drag-and-drop approach. The nodes are designed to be easy to use while retaining the flexibility needed for more advanced pipelines, making them a good fit for researchers and data scientists familiar with Python and Jupyter. **Table 2** below presents the custom Elyra nodes delivered in this release.

The Elyra nodes include both synchronous and asynchronous modes, depending on how the service is being invoked. In the synchronous approach, a Python client is instantiated (pickled) within the notebook to interact with the OSCAR Python API and invoke the service directly. This requires obtaining an EGI access token, which can be retrieved either from the EGI Notebooks environment **[egi-nb]** (if running there) or via EGI Check-in authentication. In contrast, in the asynchronous approach, the nodes obtain MinIO credentials for the target service and handle the interaction by uploading the input files to the designated input bucket and later downloading the results from the output bucket once inference is completed. This allows for decoupled execution and is suited for workloads designed to run asynchronously.

Table 2: Elyra custom nodes provided by AI4Compose.

Node	Description	Related AI model
Cowsay	Synchronous invocation of the OSCAR Cowsay service. Uses the Python client to send a text message and returns the ASCII-art output directly in the notebook.	Toy example based on the OSCAR Cowsay example .
Grayify	Synchronous invocation of the OSCAR Grayify service. Sends an image and retrieves a grayscale version.	Toy example based on the OSCAR Image Conversion to Grayscale with ImageMagick
Plant Classification	Synchronous invocation of the OSCAR Plant Species Classifier. Sends an image and returns the predicted plant species.	Uses the Plants Species Classifier model from the AI4EOSC catalog.
YOLO	Synchronous invocation of the OSCAR YOLOv8 Object Detection service. Processes an image and returns bounding boxes and class labels.	Uses the YOLOv8 model from the AI4EOSC catalog.
Body Pose	Asynchronous invocation of the OSCAR Body Pose Detection service. Uploads the image to MinIO and retrieves pose detection results from the output bucket.	Uses the Body Pose Detection model from the AI4EOSC catalog.
Thunderstorm Nowcast Microstep	Asynchronous invocation of the OSCAR Thunderstorm Nowcasting service. Uploads meteorological data or images to MinIO and retrieves nowcast predictions.	Uses the Thunderstorm nowcast (MicroStep-MIS) model from the AI4EOSC catalog. This model was developed by UC1 of WP6.
Thermal Bridge Detector	Asynchronous invocation of the OSCAR Thermal Bridge Detection service. Uploads rooftop thermal images to MinIO and retrieves detected thermal bridge regions.	Uses the Thermal Bridges on Building Rooftops Detection (TBBRDet) model from the AI4EOSC catalog. This model was developed by UC3 of WP6.
Litter Assessment	Asynchronous invocation of the OSCAR Aquatic Litter Monitoring service. Uploads drone images to MinIO and retrieves litter detection and counts.	Uses the Litter Assessment model from the AI4EOSC catalog. This model was developed by UC1 from the iImagine project.
Fish Detector	Asynchronous invocation of the OSCAR OBSEA Fish Detection service. Uploads underwater images to MinIO and retrieves detected and classified fish.	Uses the OBSEA Fish Detector model from the AI4EOSC catalog. This model was developed by UC3o from the iImagine project.

Node	Description	Related AI model
Phytoplankton	Asynchronous invocation of the OSCAR Phytoplankton Detection service. Uploads ocean images to MinIO and retrieves phytoplankton analysis results.	Uses the Phytoplankton species classifier (VLIZ) model from the AI4EOSC catalog. This model was developed by UC5 from the iMagine project.

Moreover, we have developed three custom nodes to facilitate the development of new custom nodes using the AI models of the AI4EOSC catalog, integrated with OSCAR. These supplementary nodes are:

- **Client Set-up:** Initializes the client environment in the notebook by obtaining and configuring the EGI token. Users can select whether to work with synchronous or asynchronous services. For synchronous workflows, it creates an OSCAR Python client for direct service calls. For asynchronous workflows, it configures a MinIO client to interact with input and output buckets.
- **MinIO Upload:** Uploads input files to the appropriate MinIO bucket associated with the asynchronous OSCAR service. This node is used to trigger asynchronous processing by placing the data in the service's input bucket.
- **MinIO Download:** Downloads the output files from the MinIO bucket after asynchronous processing is complete. This node retrieves the results of the asynchronous service from the output bucket for further use in the notebook.

All the Elyra nodes described in this section are publicly available in the AI4Compose GitHub repository, and a detailed tutorial on how to use them is available in the official AI4EOSC Documentation⁶.

Node-RED

For the Node-RED [[nodered](#)] and FlowFuse [[flowfuse](#)] integration, the final version of the nodes has also been completed in this second release. These nodes enable users to design and run visual workflows in a multi-tenant environment managed by FlowFuse⁷. They allow asynchronous requests to OSCAR services and make it easier to combine different models and services into a single pipeline using Node-RED's drag-and-drop interface. This approach is particularly suited for users who prefer a language-agnostic tool or need to integrate with external systems and IoT devices. The following table ([Table 3](#)) shows the definitive set of Node-RED nodes included in this release.

As with Elyra, the set of nodes is divided into synchronous and asynchronous types, depending on how they interact with the OSCAR services. Synchronous nodes directly invoke the OSCAR service and immediately return the result provided by the service in the response. In contrast, asynchronous nodes upload the input file to a MinIO bucket associated with the service, and the result is retrieved from the corresponding output bucket once the processing is complete. This design enables scalable, event-driven processing for larger or more complex tasks that benefit from decoupled execution.

⁶ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/pipelines/elyra.html>

⁷ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/pipelines/flowfuse.html>

Table 3: Node-RED custom nodes provided by AI4Compose.

Node	Description	Related AI model
Cowsay	Synchronous invocation of the OSCAR Cowsay service. Takes server URL, credentials, service name, and text (msg.payload), returns ASCII-art image with message.	Toy example based on the OSCAR Cowsay example .
Grayify	Synchronous invocation of the OSCAR Grayify service. Takes server URL, credentials, service name, and image (msg.payload), returns the grayscale image (base64) using an event-driven ImageMagick-based service.	Toy example based on the OSCAR Image Conversion to Grayscale with ImageMagick
Plant Classification	Synchronous invocation of the OSCAR Plant Species Classification service. Takes server URL, credentials, service name, and image (msg.payload), returns the predicted plant species from a 10k-species model (base64).	Uses the Plants Species Classifier model from the AI4EOSC catalog.
YOLO	Synchronous invocation of the OSCAR YOLOv8 Object Detection service. Takes server URL, credentials, service name, and image (msg.payload), returns detected objects overlaid on the image (base64).	Uses the YOLOv8 model from the AI4EOSC catalog.
Body Pose	Asynchronous invocation of the OSCAR Body Pose Detection service. Takes server URL, credentials, service name, and image (msg.payload), returns detected body pose keypoints (base64).	Uses the Body Pose Detection model from the AI4EOSC catalog.
Thermal Bridge Detector	Asynchronous invocation of the OSCAR Thermal Bridge Detector service. Takes server URL, credentials, service name, and RGB + thermal image (msg.payload), returns detected rooftop thermal bridge regions (base64), supporting energy efficiency assessments.	Uses the Thermal Bridges on Building Rooftops Detection (TBBRDet) model from the AI4EOSC catalog. This model was developed by UC3 of WP6.
Litter Assessment	Asynchronous invocation of the OSCAR Aquatic Litter Monitoring service. Takes server URL, credentials, service name, and image (msg.payload), returns an AI-driven litter analysis and count (base64), supporting standardized monitoring and citizen engagement.	Uses the Litter Assessment model from the AI4EOSC catalog. This model was developed by UC1 from the iImagine project.
Fish Detector	Asynchronous invocation of the OSCAR OBSEA Fish Detector service. Takes server URL, credentials, service name, and underwater image (msg.payload), returns	Uses the OBSEA Fish Detector model from the AI4EOSC catalog. This model was developed by UC3o from

Node	Description	Related AI model
	detected and classified fish species (base64), automating ecological monitoring at the OBSEA observatory.	the iMagine project.
Fish Detector Zip	Asynchronous invocation of the OSCAR OBSEA Fish Detector ZIP service. Takes server URL, credentials, service name, and a ZIP file of underwater images (msg.payload), returning detected and classified fish species (base64) for each image, streamlining batch ecological monitoring.	Uses the OBSEA Fish Detector model from the AI4EOSC catalog. This model was developed by UC3o from the iMagine project.
Phytoplankton	Asynchronous invocation of the OSCAR Phytoplankton Detection service. Uploads ocean images to MinIO and retrieves phytoplankton analysis results.	Uses the Phytoplankton species classifier (VLIZ) model from the AI4EOSC catalog. This model was developed by UC5 from the iMagine project.
Bird Sound Classification	Synchronous invocation of the OSCAR Bird Sound Classifier service. Takes server URL, credentials, service name, and audio file (msg.payload), returning a JSON with the top 5 predicted bird species based on a model trained on the most observed species in the Xenocanto dataset.	Uses the Bird Sound Classifier model from the AI4EOSC catalog.
Object Detection Classifier	Synchronous invocation of the OSCAR Object Detection Classifier service. Takes server URL, credentials, service name, and image (msg.payload), returning a JSON with detected objects, their bounding box coordinates, class labels, and associated probabilities above a configurable threshold.	Uses the Object detection with FasterRCNN model from the AI4EOSC catalog.
Segmentation Data	Segments video files synchronously via OSCAR. Inputs: server URL, credentials, service name, video (msg.payload), time range. Output: separate audio and video files for the selected segment.	Uses a Segmentation Data Service that divides a video into audios of n seconds and extracts frames within the video every n seconds. This node is useful in pre or post-processing tasks.

All the Node-RED nodes described in this section are publicly available in the AI4Compose GitHub repository (see [\[D5.3\]](#)), together with the examples that use them. In addition to the example pipelines for each node, we have developed a more complex pipeline that involves cross-disciplinary AI models. This pipeline, depicted in [Figure 2](#), has been tested in a cloud-to-edge environment and is part of the AI4Compose article that is currently under review in the IEEE Access journal. The pipeline starts obtaining

video files with audio integrated, separates the channels, and processes them independently. The audio is analyzed using the bird sound classifier node, while the video is processed with an object detection and classification system to identify the animals that appear. This approach combines multiple disciplines: bioacoustics and audio AI on one side, and computer vision on the other, combined with ornithology to detect the bird species.

Figure 2: Cross-disciplinary pipeline created in Node-RED.

Moreover, we have contributed to the Node-RED Library, setting up a collection for AI4Compose [\[ai4-nodered-collection\]](#), where the community can easily find our customized nodes and examples. Finally, a detailed tutorial on how to use the nodes and the Flowfuse and Node-RED tools is available in the official AI4EOSC Documentation⁸.

NEW TOOLS

In this section, we will comment on the tools that were outlined on the D5.3 Roadmap (CVAT and Kafka), as well as on the new tools that were added afterwards (NVFLARE and LLMs), supplementing the roadmap.

CVAT

As outlined in deliverable D5.3, CVAT [\[cvat\]](#) was forked from its official repository, customized, and integrated into the AI4EOSC platform to support users in the image annotation tasks⁹.

When creating a CVAT deployment from the Dashboard, users have to configure:

⁸ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/pipelines/flowfuse.html>

⁹ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/train/cvat.html>

- **CVAT credentials:** When configuring the deployment of CVAT, the user will need to enter their CVAT username and CVAT password to authenticate in the CVAT instance.
- **Storage:** For using CVAT, it is mandatory to have a storage provider linked. This is because each time a user deletes a CVAT instance a snapshot will automatically be created in their storage. When a new CVAT instance is deployed the user can either start from an existing snapshot or from a blank state (no snapshot).

In the documentation, we added guidelines on how to use CVAT and how to connect the AI4OS Storage to the CVAT instance, to automatically read data from there.

Finally, an automated periodic backup schedule is in place to avoid the loss of the time costly user annotations if the deployment was to unexpectedly fail.

Kafka

In D5.3, we planned to integrate Kafka [[kafka](#)], as a fast data streaming service.

For this we initially deploy a Kafka cluster with multiple brokers. We selected a candidate external use case (from the iMagine project [[imagine](#)], which uses the software stack developed by AI4EOSC) for testing the setup. The use case was set initially in three steps, as follows:

1. An underwater camera records the video;
2. An AI4EOSC GPU-enabled deployment processed the video with the YOLO model to extract segmentations;
3. A Youtube live stream is published.

When testing Kafka, step 1 (the camera, a.k.a the *producer*) connected to the Kafka cluster (the *broker*) to send the data. Then step 2 (the AI4EOSC deployment, a.k.a the *consumer*) connected to the broker to read the data. The last step cannot use Kafka, as we lack control over Youtube servers.

The proof-of-concept was successful, as both the producer and consumer were able to correctly interact with the Kafka brokers. Thanks to a careful analysis, it was found that the bottleneck in the pipeline was not the data transmission between steps 1 and 2, but the transmission to Youtube (step 3). Following the principles of user-driven development, as this use case finally could not benefit from using Kafka due to the constraints on the Youtube side, we decided to postpone the release of this new tool into production until we find a significant amount of users that can benefit from it.

NVFLARE

Although not initially planned in the D5.3 roadmap, following the work done in WP4, we decided to integrate NVFlare [[nvflare](#)] as an additional federated learning framework¹⁰, alongside Flower [[flower](#)]¹¹.

¹⁰ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/train/federated-nvflare.html>

¹¹ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/train/federated-flower.html>

Similar to the Flower tool, when making an NVFLARE deployment from the Dashboard, users will need to provide:

- Personal credentials to access the NVFLARE Dashboard and associated Jupyter notebook;
- Whether to make the project public or restrict the training to authorized trusted partners;
- The Docker image that includes all the necessary dependencies and configurations provided by the admin of the project;
- The start and end dates of the training.

The NVFLARE deployment will expose two endpoints, both protected with credentials:

- A dashboard used to generate the startup kits for the server, admins and clients. The startup kits include the configurations and certificates required to establish secure connections between the FL servers, FL clients, and admin clients. These files are essential for verifying identity and enforcing authorization policies between the server and clients;
- A Jupyter notebook, from where you can start the federated server.

In the documentation, we provide guides on how to add new clients to the training and getting started with NVFLARE.

Small LLMs

Although not initially planned in the D5.3 Roadmap, adapting to the user uptake of Generative AI, we decided to add support for users for users to self-deploy their own LLMs¹².

This new tool is complementary to the platform-wide deployed LLM instance (see [AI4OS LLM](#)), which is deployed with a very similar software stack.

Although not deployed of such powerful GPUs, the self-deployed has several benefits of the platform-wide LLM:

- It lets users choose the model they want to deploy, from a wide variety of models from a catalog;
- Resources are exclusively dedicated to the user and their selected coworkers;
- Users are admins, so you they configure model and UI parameters;
- Users are admins, so they can create their own Knowledge Bases as persistent memory banks;
- Users are admins, so they can use Functions to create their own agents that use custom prompts, custom Knowledge Bases, and custom input/output filtering.

USER CENTRIC DASHBOARD

First, regarding the features we promised in Deliverable 5.3 [\[D5.3\]](#), the AI4EOSC Dashboard¹³ now includes a **Statistics section** (named Dashboard section in the previous deliverable), which shows the statistics of the user deployments as well as

¹² <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/deploy/llm.html>

¹³ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/reference/dashboard.html>

some cluster related statistics. Its interfaces and details remain the same as those mentioned in D5.3.

In order to improve the navigation between the different modules and tools of the platform and alongside the introduction of the new metadata, we **redesigned the Marketplace** of the Dashboard (now called Catalog) and their detailed view (check **Figure 3** and **Figure 4**, respectively).

Figure 3: Modules catalog view in the AI4EOOSC Dashboard.

Figure 4: AI4EOOSC module detail view.

Now there are **filtering options** so that the elements of the catalog can be filtered by: libraries, tasks, platform categories, data types and tags (refer to [Figure 4](#) and [Figure 5](#)), according to the changes in the new module's metadata (see [New code repositories](#) for more details). These filters can be applied individually or can be concatenated, so that multiple filters are applied at the same time. Apart from that, they can be sorted by name or by most recent.

This new option is available for the modules and tools in the AI4EOSC marketplace, but not for the LLMs or the AI4Life Marketplace. This is because the latter two do not follow the metadata schema ([New code repositories](#)). Nevertheless, they can still be filtered using the search bar to look for matches in the titles and descriptions of the modules.

Figure 5: Applied filters detail.

Regarding deployments, we have included an option to **track the CO2 consumption** of the deployments which use the Federated Learning with Flower tool ([Figure 6](#)). This has been implemented using the CodeCarbon Python library [[codecarbon](#)].

Figure 6: Configuration form of the Federated Learning Server with the Flower software.

As part of the continuous expansion of supported tools, and in addition to the CVAT tool mentioned in the previous deliverable, several **new tools** have been integrated (check Figure 7 to see CVAT detailed view). These are described in detail in the **New Tools** section.

Figure 7: CVAT Image Annotation tool detail view.

To simplify the deployment process for users, we have implemented a one-click deployment button in the Dashboard (Figure 8). This triggers a call to PAPI, which

automatically creates a service on the **OSCAR inference** platform. All services created by a user are conveniently listed in the Dashboard for easy access and management.

Figure 8: Inference button inside AI4EOOSC module detail view.

Moreover, users can now **link their Nextcloud accounts** directly from the Dashboard, once linked, their credentials are automatically populated in the configuration forms, making setup faster and easier. Through the profile section, users can select and connect their preferred storage provider (Figure 9). Later, when creating a deployment, they simply choose from the linked providers, enabling a faster and more seamless workflow (Figure 10).

Figure 9: Profile section.

Figure 10: Data configuration section

We have also integrated **Hugging Face support**. In such respect, users can view and manage their Hugging Face token directly from their profile (refer to Figure 9). When deploying an LLM that requires authentication, the token is automatically pre-filled in the corresponding field, streamlining the setup process (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Configuration form of an LLM deployment.

Apart from the previously announced features, we have also implemented more improvements to the Dashboard, following the **New PAPI functionalities**:

- **Deployment to EOSC Node:** users can now deploy modules directly using cloud resources provided by the EOSC EU Node [\[eu-node\]](#), expanding the available infrastructure options;
- **Batch deployment:** the Dashboard supports deploying modules in batch mode, which translates into a more efficient utilization of cluster resources;
- **Snapshots creation:** users can create snapshots of their deployments, enabling easier backup and recovery;
- **LLM catalog:** a new catalog of large language models (LLMs) has been added, allowing users to browse available models and deploy them directly from the Dashboard;
- **Integration with AI4LLM:** chatbot interface within the Dashboard which enables direct interaction with the AI4LLM instance [\[ai4-llm\]](#). This assistant helps users resolve questions about the platform and its usage;
- **Integration with Provenance:** users can now view the provenance graph of the modules and download the corresponding RDF files directly from the Dashboard.

MODEL AND DATA VERSIONING

The MLflow service to track experiments and version models is already running in production and serving users¹⁴.

For the second release **MLflow Model Registry has been used to store AI models** as artifacts with a specific version (using alias and tags) and shared across different team members. As well the datasets used as input during training and testing has been tracked as it is shown in [Figure 12](#).

Figure 12: MLflow Experiment-run example where input dataset is tracked

We have **integrated MLflow UI with the Vault secret management** to secure the MLflow user credentials. In doing so, users do not need to provide their credentials for each

¹⁴ <https://docs.ai4eosoc.eu/en/latest/howtos/develop/mlflow.html>

new deployment on the platform because they are automatically injected in their development environment such as Jupyter Notebook or VSCode. Securing the credentials in Vault has also enabled better retrieval of the information when generating the provenance files (see [Model Provenance](#)).

To further enhance the knowledge graph generated by the provenance solution with information tracked from MLflow like the metrics, parameters, model version lineage, we **deployed an MLflow user agent** that automatically assigns read permissions to all existing and newly created experiments and registered models.

We couldn't interface the AI4EOSC dashboard with MLflow because it is not possible to store MLflow credentials (especially the password) in the browser due to privacy/security concerns.

DRIFT MONITORING TOOLS

Following the Roadmap in D5.3, we have developed DriftWatch¹⁵.

DriftWatch is a **drift monitoring service** that aims to provide users with a database where they can store and visualise the trend of statistical properties of their data (i.e. p-values for drift analysis)]. It can be used to detect where the statistical properties of the data change, meaning that the inference results are no longer trustworthy and an action needs to be taken by the user (clean the detector, retrain the model, etc).

Secured with OpenID Connect, the authentication provides compatibility with AI4EOSC authentication (see [New authentication](#)) and fine-grained access control for groups, scopes and claims.

The drift-watch service is composed by a Python client that the users can install in their AI modules to collect the drift metrics from within their pipelines. We provide tutorials on how to train a drift detector (based on our own Frouros package [\[frouros\]](#) for example) and send the metrics with the driftwatch client.

Once the metrics are collected, they can use the Driftwatch graphical user interface designed to streamline drift monitoring and analysis. This user-friendly interface provides advanced functionality through several key components:

The *interface* displays drift records in an organised table format for each experiment, enabling users to easily track and manage their monitoring activities across different projects.

Each *drift record* contains detailed information including:

- **Creation Date:** Timestamp showing when the drift detection was initiated;
- **Status:** Real-time monitoring state (completed, running, or failed);
- **Drift:** Clear indication of whether drift was detected (Yes/No);
- **Domain Tags:** Customisable labels for categorizing drift types based on specific use cases (e.g., data-drift, concept-drift);
- **Execution Mode:** Processing approach specification (streaming or batch);
- **Algorithm:** Detection method employed (e.g., DDM, ADWIN, KSWIN);

¹⁵ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/develop/drift-watch.html>

- **Actions:** Interactive buttons for detailed record examination and management.

The interface includes sophisticated filtering capabilities that allow users to:

- Filter records by tags to focus on specific drift types or experiments;
- Select from multiple visualisation options to graphically represent drift patterns;
- Customize plot parameters and graph types for optimal data interpretation;
- Generate comprehensive visual summaries of drift detection results across time periods.

Figure 13: Data drift visualisation of the OBSEA-FISH Detector Model from AI4EOSC Catalog

In **Figure 13** we display the results from the OBSEA Fish Detector model **[jobsea-fish]** from the AI4EOSC catalog. It shows a drift detector signal stating that the underwater camera is dirty (the red data points in the plot) and that it needs cleaning. This model was developed by the OBSEA Fish Detection usecase from the iMagine project **[imagine]**.

MODEL PROVENANCE

As stated in the D5.3 Roadmap, we have developed and put in production the new provenance system for the AI modules¹⁶.

Now, each time the CI/CI pipeline is launched, we automatically parse info from different Platform components:

- **Jenkins**: we extract build information, like code quality tests or docker image hashes;
- **Nomad**: we extract training information, like what were the computing resources used to train a given module;
- **MLflow**: we extract experiment logging information, like the hyper-parameters used in the different training runs;
- **PAPI**: we extract module metadata.

All this information is saved in a single RDF file that explains the connection between the different components, like how the Nomad deployment used a given dataset for training the module, or how Jenkins generated a new Harbor docker image.

For an improved user experience, we show in the Dashboard the final provenance chain in an interactive graph form, as shown in **Figure 14**.

¹⁶ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/reference/modules.html#provenance>

Figure 14: Graph visualization of the provenance RDF file of an AI module.

MODEL METADATA TOOLS

As stated in the D5.3 Roadmap, we developed a set of tools to handle the different processing needs when dealing with our metadata [\[ai4os-metadata\]](#):

- To handle the conversion between different file formats (like JSON or YAML);
- To do semantic versioning of the metadata, by defining different metadata JSON schemas that continuously evolve to adapt to the platform needs;
- To validate any metadata file against a particular version;
- To map between different profiles and formats, like mapping to JSON-LD and Turtle using the MLDCAT-AP profile [\[mldcat-ap\]](#). This feature was developed in collaboration with the SEMIC support center [\[semic\]](#). The resulting RDF can be visualized in [Figure 15](#).

[metadata](#)

📁 metadata

Types:

iri6:MachineLearningModel

RDF Rank:

0

🔍 Search instance properties

Building Rooftops. In Sci Data 10, 268 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02140-z> ^{en}

dct:title
Thermal Bridges on Building Rooftops Detection (TBRDet)
en

dcat:keyword
deep learning ^{en} [Show 3 more](#) ^{en}

- instance segmentation ^{en}
- multi-spectral data ^{en}
- object detection ^{en}

dct:created
2024-07-18 ^{xsd:date}

dct:identifier
thermal-bridges-rooftops-detector

dct:modified
2024-12-05 ^{xsd:date}

Figure 15: Graph visualization of the RDF file resulting from integration with the MLDCAT-AP profile [semic-repo].

TRAIN BATCH MODE

Although it was not initially planned in the D5.3 Roadmap, during the second half of the project we released a new training workflow: batch mode training¹⁷.

In contrast with standard mode training, where users launch a persistent deployment that they access interactively, users can now launch a deployment that runs the training according to a script they provide. Once the training is completed, the deployment is deleted and resources are freed. The outputs of the training are still saved in the connected user storage.

By adopting batch mode training we can use GPU resources much more efficiently, making sure that they are always in use for training, and move the development to CPU resources.

AI4OS LLM

Although not initially planned in the D5.3 Roadmap [D5.3], seeing the uptake of Generative AI-based solutions and in response to the demand of our users, we have developed a service to serve LLMs to users via a user-friendly UI.

In addition to the standard chat features of any LLM chatbot, we have created a dedicated knowledge base (based on the AI4OS documentation) that allows the model to provide grounded answers to users that have questions on how to use the platform.

By serving a small catalog of LLM models in dedicated GPUs, we are offering a reliable service that our users are able to integrate with their external tools. For this we have provided instructions on how to use the service from Python and how to integrate the code suggestion in VScode.

¹⁷ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/train/batch.html>

Finally we have integrated the LLM-based service with other components, allowing for example to chat directly from the Dashboard or a preliminary integration to ask the chatbot to explain the provenance of a model from the provenance graph.

NEW AUTHENTICATION

During this second release we rolled out a new authentication system based on Keycloak [\[keycloak\]](#), moving away from EGI Check-In [\[legi-checkin\]](#). This move was propagated across all WP5 that have adapted to start using it.

This new system was deployed to accelerate the onboarding of external communities¹⁸ to the platform (as their own authentication can be federated in our system) and to improve the management of the software stack. Now, clients for different services can be created faster and we have a more fine grained control of the different services users have access to, through the creation of a role based system.

To still maintain backward compatibility, EGI Check-In is one of the federated identities in the new system, along with many others like EDUGain [\[edugain\]](#), GitHub [\[github\]](#), Google Accounts [\[google-accounts\]](#), etc.

4 - USER JOURNEYS TO THE PLATFORM

In this section we will provide a brief overview of many standard workflows that users follow when interacting with the platform. We will highlight how many of these workflows make use of the features described in the previous section.

All over the text, we will link the dedicated tutorials in the documentation [\[ai4-docs\]](#) (often accompanied by short video tutorials) where more in-depth information can be found.

TRY A MODEL

The *Try a model* workflow¹⁹ is the entrypoint for many users to the platform.

When a new user discovers the platform, they usually want to test the AI module capabilities before committing to become a project member. For this, they explore the Dashboard Marketplace and decide on the module they want to test.

Once selected, they have two options to try the module:

First, they can **try the model locally**²⁰. Since all modules are publicly available on DockerHub, users can retrieve the image link from the module page and run the model locally with docker. This will expose the model API together with a Swagger UI where the users can make predictions.

¹⁸ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/getting-started/register.html>

¹⁹ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/try/index.html>

²⁰ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/try/locally.html>

Second, they can **try the model directly from the Dashboard**²¹. For this they will need to register an account (basic accounts are open to everyone). Then in the module page, they can click the “Try” button that will create a temporary deployment of this module, on limited resources. It will expose a Gradio interface (and an API) that users can leverage to make predictions with the model.

Related new AI4EOSC 2 features:

- [Try-me endpoints](#)
- [User centric Dashboard](#)
- [New PAPI functionalities](#)
- [New Authentication](#)

DEVELOP A MODEL

Once a user becomes a member of the project, they might want to *develop a new model*²² and to include it in the Marketplace.

After creating an account on the platform, users need to first create a template for the code, using our Module Template generator. Then, going to the Dashboard, they can create an “AI4OS Development Environment” selecting:

- The Deep Learning framework they want to use (eg. Pytorch, Tensorflow);
- The IDE they want to use (eg. VSCode, JupyterLab);
- The storage they want to connect with;
- The hardware resources they want to use.

Once the deployment is created, they can copy the module template and start adding the code. User have in particular to take care of:

- Defining the train and predict function in the model API;
- Define module tests;
- Edit the module Dockerfile;
- Edit the module metadata.

Once the code is ready, it can be pushed into GitHub and added to the catalog index. Thus, the module will be integrated in the Marketplace.

Related new AI4EOSC 2 features:

- [New code repositories](#)
- [Model metadata tools](#)
- [AI4OS LLM](#)
- [Small LLMs](#)
- [User centric Dashboard](#)
- [New PAPI functionalities](#)
- [New Authentication](#)

²¹ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/try/dashboard-gradio.html>

²² <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/develop/index.html>

TRAIN A MODEL

Once a model has been integrated in the Marketplace it's time to *Train the model*²³.

After logging into the Dashboard, the users land in the module they want to retrain. Then they have two options to train their model.

On the one hand, users can choose to **train it in standard mode**²⁴. In this case, they create a persistent deployment with GPU resources and connected to storage. Via an IDE they can run the training and save their new model.

On the other hand, users can choose to **train it in batch mode**²⁵. In this case, they create a temporary deployment also connected to GPU resources and to storage. This deployment will run a user provided script and when the training is completed will shutdown, thus freeing the resources.

In either standard or batch mode, users can profit from our **MLflow experiment tracking** instance to track their trainings and register their models²⁶. For that they need to make sure that the module was developed to support MLflow logging, by registering the proper variables in the training loop.

In addition to standard and batch mode trainings, users can train their models in a distributed way among different resources and with data distributed in different locations under a **federated learning**²⁷ architecture. For this they need to go to the Tools section in the Dashboard and deploy one of the two federated learning frameworks we support: Flower²⁸ or NVFLARE²⁹. Once they have configured the experiment and deployed the Federated Learning server, they can create the federated learning clients with their module code to train their models in a federated fashion.

Finally no training tutorial can be complete without mentioning data preparation. In case users are dealing with a computer vision based module, they can go to the Dashboard and deploy a **CVAT instance to annotate data**³⁰. This instance will allow users to connect their storage and start annotating there.

Related new AI4EOSC 2 features:

- **CVAT**
- **Model metadata tools**
- **Model and data versioning**
- **NVFLARE**
- **Train batch mode**
- **External integrations**
- **Model provenance**
- **User centric Dashboard**

²³ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/train/index.html>

²⁴ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/train/standard.html>

²⁵ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/train/batch.html>

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³⁰ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/train/cvat.html>

- **New PAPI functionalities**
- **New Authentication**

DEPLOY A MODEL

Finally, once a trained model is in the marketplace, it's time to *Deploy the model* in production³¹. Once they log into the module page in the Dashboard, users have several options.

Authenticated users have two main options:

- They can deploy their modules in **serverless mode**³². For this they can create a service, selecting the amount of resources they want to devote to the service. Once created, they can invoke the service via synchronous calls, via asynchronous calls (by uploading the inference inputs to a MinIO storage and retrieving the outputs when completed) or via the default OSCAR service UI.
- They can deploy their modules in **dedicated mode**³³. For this they can create a persistent deployment. Once deployed, they will be able to query the model through a dedicated Gradio UI.

Un-authenticated users have two main options:

- They can use the Infrastructure Manager (IM) to **deploy the model in any external cloud**³⁴. For this they would need to connect to the Infrastructure Manager, provide their external cloud credentials and create a deployment that will expose the module's API.
- They can use their researcher credentials to **deploy the module in the EU Node**³⁵. For this they have to choose whether to deploy as a container or as a VM, allocate some computing resources and then deploy the module, that will expose again the module's API.

In addition to the above mentioned deployment options, authenticated users can **create AI workflows** by composing several modules, along with preprocessing and postprocessing options. For this they have to choose which workflow composition tool they want to use, either FlowFuse³⁶ or Elyra³⁷, and start visually attaching the workflow building blocks.

Related new AI4EOSC 2 features:

- **Inference endpoints**
- **Drift monitoring tools**
- **AI4Compose implementation (Elyra, NodeRed)**
- **External integrations**
- **User centric Dashboard**
- **New PAPI functionalities**

³¹ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/deploy/overview.html>

³² <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/deploy/oscar.html>

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³⁴ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/deploy/cloud.html>

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³⁶ <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/en/latest/howtos/pipelines/flowfuse.html>

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5 - CONCLUSION

This deliverable explored all the different WP5 new features implemented during the second part of the project. From the above, we conclude that we have successfully delivered all the features outlined in the previous roadmap, as well as additional features that were not initially planned, but that have emerged in a natural way from our commitment to quickly adapt the platform to the fast evolving AI ecosystem.

Looking at the initial roadmap, the following components, functionalities and/or actions have been successfully integrated into the platform: new code repositories, new PAPI functionalities, external integrations, try-me endpoints, inference endpoints, AI4Compose implementation, integration of new tools (including CVAT and Kafka), user-centric dashboard, model and data versioning, integration of drift monitoring tools, model provenance and model metadata tools. In addition, we have integrated the AI4OS LLMs service, the batch mode training and we have adopted a new authentication system.

Finally, throughout this report we demonstrated that all these features are pieces of the same puzzle forming a unified view, showing how they can be seamlessly integrated into coherent user workflows.

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[nvflare] NVIDIA NVFLARE: <https://developer.nvidia.com/flare>

[nodered] NodeRed: <https://nodered.org/>

[obsea-fish] OBSEA fish detection usecase:
<https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/catalog/modules/obsea-fish-detection>

[oscar] Open Source Serverless Computing for Data-Processing Applications (OSCAR):
<https://oscar.grycap.net/>

[pytest] Pytest, <https://docs.pytest.org/en/stable/>

[semic] SEMIC Support Centre,
<https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/semic-support-centre>

[semic-repo] Code repository for the pilot integration by SEMIC:
<https://github.com/SEMICEu/EOSC-MLDCAT-AP-Pilot>

[tox] Tox, <https://tox.wiki/en/4.27.0/>

[turtle] RDF 1.1 Turtle: <https://www.w3.org/TR/turtle/>

[zenodo] Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/>

